

Title: Providers' willingness to sacrifice earnings for better patient outcomes is associated with higher quality of care

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ABSTRACT:

OBJECTIVES: Standard theories of health provider behavior suggest that providers are motivated by both profit and patient health benefit. Detailed empirical data are seldom available to measure marginal rates of substitution (MRS) between profit and patient health outcomes. Furthermore, it is difficult to empirically assess how these relative preferences affect quality of care.

METHODS: This study uses a unique dataset from rural Myanmar to assess heterogeneous preferences toward treatment efficacy relative to provider profit and the impact of these preferences on the quality of provider diagnosis and treatment. Using conjoint survey data from 187 providers, we estimated the marginal utilities of higher treatment efficacy and of higher profit, and the MRS between these outcomes. We also measured the quality of diagnosis and treatment for malaria among these providers using a previously validated observed patient simulation.

RESULTS: There is substantial heterogeneity in provider willingness to substitute greater treatment efficacy for higher profits. Higher preferences for treatment efficacy are positively associated with the quality of treatment among providers, and higher preferences for profit are negatively associated with quality of diagnosis. We found no consistent effect of provider MRS on quality of care.

CONCLUSIONS: Our findings suggest that providers vary in their preferences towards profit and treatment efficacy, with those providers that place greater weight on treatment efficacy providing higher quality of care. This suggests that incentive schemes that are not purely financial may have a role in increasing quality of care.

JEL Codes: I1, I180, I110, J330

I. INTRODUCTION

Theories of health provider behavior suggest that providers are motivated not only by their own earnings, but also by altruism, a willingness to behave in a way that benefits another, at one's own expense (Nagel, 1970; Forsythe et al., 1994; Andreoni and Miller, 2002). In the context of the patient-provider relationship, this translates into trading off profits for patient health benefit (Arrow, 1963; Ellis and McGuire, 1986; Woodward and Warren-Boulton, 1984; Farley, 1986; Godager and Wiesen, 2013). Altruistic behavior may be motivated by multiple factors, including reciprocity, in which an altruistic individual feels the need to "return the favor" (Rabin, 1993), or by perceived expectations of others or social norms (Bicchieri & Xiao, 2010). Professional ethical standards may play a significant role in motivating altruistic behavior among health providers; physicians in many countries are required to adopt the Hippocratic Oath, stating "I will apply, for the benefit of the sick, all measures which are required, avoiding those twin traps of overtreatment and therapeutic nihilism" (Lasagna, 1964; Edelstein, 1943).

The theory of altruistic health provider behavior is supported by an evidence base of largely self-reported survey and interview data, discrete choice experiments, prescription records, field experiments, and lab experiments (Galizzi et al. 2015). The classical experimental approach to demonstrate altruism has been based on strategic games such as the ultimatum game (Guth et al., 1982) and the dictator game (Kahneman et al., 1986), which involve deciding on how to divide a sum of money between players. In both games, individuals agree to arrangements which differ from predicted equilibria of purely self-motivated proposals, although there is some heterogeneity in this effect (Galizzi et al. 2015; Camerer, 2003).

While these findings do suggest that altruism is one important motivator among health providers, empirical evidence on trading off profits for patient benefit is somewhat limited (Serra, 2010; Heikkila et al., 2015; Allaby, 2003, Kahler and Soule, 1991). Studies of medical students and physicians suggest that these individuals vary in their responsiveness to income (Scott, 2001; Rizzo and Zeckhauser, 2007) and additional work has suggested that medical students are significantly more altruistic than non-medical students in an experimental settings (Hennig-Schmidt, 2014). Godager and Wiesen (2013) report similar findings, using an abstracted experimental setting to explicitly estimate the weights medical students attach to profits and patient benefit. They find that while nearly all students place some positive weight on patient benefit, the relative value of profits versus patient benefit varies greatly. To our knowledge, there is not a substantial literature that describes these tradeoffs among fully trained providers and explores how these preferences affect care.

The altruistic physician assumption has been widely adopted, and is often critical in the design of models of payment mechanisms and other health policy reforms (Ellis and McGuire, 1986; Chalkley and Malcomson, 1998). If providers act as perfect agents for patients, we might intuitively expect provider behavior to be perfectly aligned with patient benefit. In this context, implementing a fully prospective payment mechanism (versus a cost-based reimbursement) would not affect patient outcomes (Ellis and McGuire, 1986). However, if providers undervalue patient benefits, a prospective payment system is likely to lead to an undersupply of services. A mixed reimbursement system has been proposed, but the optimal design and level of supply-side cost-sharing will still depend on the intensity of physician benevolence (Chalkley and Malcomson, 1998).

While the effects of payment mechanism on the quantity and quality of care provided have been modeled (Kaarboe and Siciliani, 2011; Eggleston, 2005; Siciliani, 2009), models that comprehensively account for variation in provider altruism have been limited. Both provider earnings and patient health benefit require costly effort and are not always produced homothetically as effort is supplied. If providers vary in their marginal rate of substitution (MRS) between profits and patient benefit, theory suggests that those providers with a greater relative preference towards patient benefit will undertake more costly efforts to achieve better quality. Furthermore, the relative preferences of providers may mediate their responses to alternative payment mechanisms. Some economic models have suggested that directly appealing to preferences of providers towards positive patient outcomes may be one approach to promote high quality of care (Eggleston, 2005).

Empirical assessments of the relationship between provider altruism and the quality of care provided require unusually detailed data. This study relies on a unique dataset that simultaneously captures explicit tradeoffs between profit and patient benefit *and* measures of the quality of the diagnostic and treatment choices made by these individuals. These data allow us to build upon existing evidence of variation in altruism across providers to better understand the implications of this variation for patient care. Our data come from informal sector private providers in rural Myanmar. Low- and middle-income country (LMIC) health care systems often rely on informal private providers for a large share of service provision and are systematic efforts to promote higher quality services are difficult to design (Kruk, Larson, and Twum-Danso, 2016). Designing incentive compatible mechanisms to improve private sector quality in LMICs will require an improved understanding of provider motivations. A link between provider altruism and improved quality would suggest that there may be value in policies that promote altruism in the clinical workforce.

We characterize altruism by a willingness to trade off profit for treatment efficacy (patient health benefit), and assess this trade-off using a conjoint survey among 187 private health providers, who had been recruited into a broader study to assess the impact of a financial incentive schemes on the uptake of rapid diagnostic tests for malaria (Aung et al., 2015). Technical quality of care was assessed among the same providers using a previously validated pediatric patient simulation. These data allow us to empirically assess variation in the degree of altruism among health providers, as well as to examine the relationship between altruism and quality of care.

The paper will proceed as follows. In Section II, we lay out two potential models to describe provider behavior in a context of a provider selling a medication to a patient. In Section III, we define the structure of the conjoint survey to elicit preferences among health providers, and we outline the process for assessing technical quality of care. Section IV describes our results, and in Section V, we conclude and place these findings within the context of related work.

II. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

We begin by introducing competing models of provider behavior, and we define altruism within this framework. We then describe our approach to testing which model is most consistent with observed behavior. In this simplified scenario, we focus only on two agents – the provider and the patient. We assume that the provider’s primary decision is regarding the quantity of medication to prescribe to a patient. In this stylized context, the quantity of medication offered is a measure of the quality of care provided; medication is helpful to an extent but harmful after a certain point. We further assume that patient health benefit is fully determined by the quality of care, but that the patient experiences asymmetric information such that demand for care is determined purely by price. The health outcome of the patient, $H(M)$, is a biphasic function of medication, with patient health benefit maximized at an optimal point denoted by M^* . In the context of rural Myanmar, health workers in the private sector generate their revenue mostly through drug sales rather than through provider fees. Therefore, the provider’s profit is also directly related to the quantity of medication prescribed. We assume that patients have no ability to judge the quality of the care they receive and demand for medication is simply $M(P_m)$. With demand unrelated to service quality, the assumptions predict that higher technical quality of care (prescribing a quantity of medication closer to M^*) would not necessarily increase provider profits. Furthermore, if providing quality care is costly, quality would be undersupplied.

Within the confines of these simplifying assumptions we can outline two plausible models for how a provider would choose the quantity of medication to supply:

Model A (the purely profit-maximizing health provider): Under this model, the provider is purely financially interested, and acts only to maximize profits. As equation [1] displays, provider utility U_A depends on profits π , which are a linear function of revenue and cost. Revenue is defined by the product of the exogenous price P_m and the quantity (M) of medicine sold. Cost is a function of the prices of various provider inputs, including labor P_l , capital P_k , and wholesale goods P_w .

$$[1] U_A = \pi = P_m \times M(P_m) - C(M, P_l, P_k, P_w)$$

In this model, a profit-maximizing provider will maximize U_A , setting the quantity supplied at the point that marginal revenue equals marginal cost. There is no mechanism that would move an equilibrium of purely selfish providers and uninformed patients towards an equilibrium in the neighborhood of the patients' optimal M^* .

Model B (the altruistic health provider): In this model, the provider has a utility function U_B which incorporates the profit generated from the sale of medication π and the health outcomes of the patient $H(M)$. The altruistic provider is therefore motivated to prescribe medications that offer both a high profit and also an effective treatment for their patients. The model is presented in equation [2]:

$$[2] U_B = U_B(\pi, H(M))$$

The optimal supply of M in this model depends on a tradeoff between π and $H(M)$. Profit will be an increasing function of M at all values of M , but patient benefit, $H(M)$, will start to decline for values of $M > M^*$. By assumption, the functional form of $H(M)$ will restrain the supply of M because $\frac{\partial U_B}{\partial H} \frac{\partial H}{\partial M}$ is negative for values beyond the health-producing optimum. We can define the marginal rate of substitution (MRS) between patient health benefit and profit as the ratio of the marginal utility of $H(M)$ to the marginal utility of π .

Measurements of the marginal utility of health, marginal utility of profit and the MRS would help empirically distinguish the two behavioral models. In Model A, $MRS_{H,\pi} = \frac{\partial U_A / \partial H}{\partial U_A / \partial \pi} = 0$. In Model B, $MRS_{H,\pi} = \frac{\partial U_B / \partial H}{\partial U_B / \partial \pi}$, and would be expected to be non-zero, with magnitude dependent on the functional form of U_B . Since $H(M)$ and π are themselves functions of medication quantity dispensed, M , with $\frac{\partial H}{\partial M} > 0$ for $M < M^*$, $\frac{\partial H}{\partial M} < 0$ for $M > M^*$, and $\frac{\partial \pi}{\partial M} > 0$ for all M , it is clear that the rate of substitution between health benefit and profit is correlated

with the quantity of medicine provided. Figure 1 illustrates this point by showing indifference curves with $MRS_{H,\pi} = 0$ in Panel A and $MRS_{H,\pi} > 0$ in Panel B. In both panels there is a production possibility curve for H and π that would emerge if $H(M)$ were biphasic. In Panel A, there is no effect of the MRS on setting the optimal supply of M . In Panel B, however, the optimal M depends on the MRS. The practical implication is that the technical quality of drug dispensing by a provider will be determined by the structure of the provider's utility function.

Empirical tests differentiating Model A of purely profit-seeking health providers from Model B of altruistic providers require a mechanism to observe tradeoffs between provider profit and patient health benefit. To further show that altruistic preferences affect the quality of medication dispensing will require simultaneous observations of the quality of care they are providing. In this study, we will use treatment efficacy as a measure of patient health benefit. Our stated preference measures of $U'(H)$ and $U'(\pi)$ will be used to first test whether $U'(H) = 0$, as stipulated in Model A of purely profit seeking providers. If we find $U'(H) > 0$ and $U'(\pi) > 0$, we can test the prediction that $MRS_{H,\pi}$ is positively correlated with the quality of care in provider recommendations for treatment. We will obtain measures of quality of care from an observed simulated patient encounter protocol.

III. METHODS

III.A. Provider Preference Measurement

Provider preferences towards profits, treatment efficacy (patient health benefit), and patient financial impact were evaluated using a conjoint survey in rural Myanmar. In conjoint analyses, respondents are asked to state their preferences between a selection of product profiles, where each profile is defined by a set of components, or “attributes”, which take on different possible levels. By examining the choices that respondents make between alternative profiles, the underlying preference structure and the implicit values for a particular attribute can be estimated. Specifically, the conjoint approach allows us to estimate the utilities associated with levels of profit, treatment efficacy, and patient financial impact. Conjoint analysis was first introduced by Green and Rao (1971) and is now widely used in marketing studies, often when choices in an actual market cannot be observed. This approach has been applied to a variety of health-related topics, as well, including those in low- and middle-income contexts (Mangham et al., 2009; Johnson et al., 2013).

In our study, the providers were 187 informal health care providers from 104 villages across 3 townships in the Mon and Kayin states of rural Myanmar, and consisted of drug sellers, chemists, village doctors, traditional healers,

and pharmacists. In this part of rural Myanmar, formally trained physicians were extremely scarce. Furthermore, at this time, the provision of primarily health services in this region by Myanmar government was limited. The providers in our study were all members of a social franchise called the Sun Quality Network operated by the NGO Populations Services International (PSI). Each of the providers had received prior training in the management of malaria. Each received regular visits from a franchise supervisor to offer subsidized antimalarial drugs at wholesale prices that they would provide to patients at a mark-up. They received no direct salary and subsisted on their collection of revenue from selling medications at retail prices in excess of their costs.

The conjoint survey used a series of 18 choice sets to understand provider preferences towards hypothetical pharmaceutical treatments for a 5-year-old child presenting with lower respiratory infection and fever. For each choice set, providers were presented with three alternative hypothetical medications that they could dispense. In each choice set, the alternative medications were described by three attributes: profits for the provider, treatment efficacy, and share of the medication cost that was to be paid by the patient (financial burden). These attributes varied across a range, with each alternative defined by a specific level for each attribute. Profit could be either “very low”, “low”, “middle”, “high”, or “very high.” Efficacy could be either 85% or 95%, and financial burden could be either 0%, 50% or 100%. While other attributes are likely to affect provider decision-making, these attributes were selected based on our definition of provider altruism.

Levels were designed to be context-appropriate and to decrease respondent cognitive burden. Providers were told that, on average, their profit in this scenario would be around 150TK (USD \$0.15), but they could make a higher or lower profit by choosing among the alternative medications. Based on PSI’s administrative data, this profit level was just slightly above the average expected profit per child health visit of \$0.12 (Bishai, Lefevre, Theuss et al., 2013). While each respondent might have a slightly different subjective interpretation of the monetary value of each profit level, we found that this categorical framing of profit was less burdensome for respondents.

The description of efficacy for each alternative medication did not provide clinical detail about any long-term disability or mortality. The scenario stipulated that the worst outcome for the child was the need to seek referral at a hospital. In pilot testing, we found that adding emotionally significant details about children’s potential suffering or death slowed down and distracted the participants’ responses. The wording to explain the levels of effectiveness was as follows: “Sometimes the effectiveness is 95% which means that out of 100 children taking the

drug, 95 will improve and 5 will get worse and need to go to a hospital. Sometimes the effectiveness is 85% which means that out of 100 that 15 will get worse and will need to go to a hospital.”

The share of medication cost the patient was responsible for was included as an attribute in the survey to assess preferences of providers towards the financial burden placed upon patients. Although we designed this question to assess preferences towards financial protection, we learned during the study that many providers were interpreting this attribute as the certainty they would receive payment. In rural Myanmar, third party payers are often informal members of the community who might vouch for payment, but these payers are not always reliable. By the time this was apparent, it was too late to change the survey and still have an adequate sample size. It is also possible that this misinterpretation affected our measurement of preferences toward profit. This is a limitation of our study. Therefore, since this product attribute did not have a clear interpretation, we control for financial burden in our results, but refrain from interpreting responses to it as an indicator of altruism or concern for patient’s financial protection in our primary analysis. We do, however, describe the distribution of these preferences in Appendix Figure A1.

We chose to use choice sets of three alternatives each based on field piloting to balance respondent burden with efficiency. With one attribute using five levels, one using three levels, and one attribute using two levels, there could have been a total of $\binom{30}{3} = 4060$ possible combinations of three alternatives. The particular combination of 18 choice sets and arrangement of attribute levels in the design was selected using Sawtooth Version 3 CBC software to achieve a practical mix of orthogonality, level balance, and minimal overlap while keeping respondent burden reasonable. These desirable features of conjoint surveys have been described by the International Society for Pharmacoeconomics and Outcomes Research Conjoint Analysis Experimental Design Good Research Practices Task Force (Johnson et al., 2013). According to these guidelines, even if designs are nearly balanced and nearly orthogonal, they are usually still identified. For each choice set, providers were asked to select which medication from the set they would actually sell to a patient. The choice of one hypothetical pharmaceutical treatment over the others revealed the preferences of each provider over the specified attribute levels. An example of one choice set is provided in Figure 2. A schematic of the data set-up is shown in the Appendix Table A1.

In 15 of 18 choice sets, higher efficacy came at the expense of lower provider profit or greater financial burden for the family. The remaining three choice sets were designed to be “logic tests” and included one alternative that dominated the other two, by offering higher profit, higher efficacy and lower patient spending.

To better ensure reporting of true preferences, respondents were told only that the survey would assess their preferences and tradeoffs, and there was no mention of measuring their degree of altruism. Further, respondents were assured that their identities would be safeguarded. Because there were 18 choice sets with multiple attributes, it would not be obvious to either the respondent or the enumerator that any particular stated preference would be socially acceptable or suggestive of an “altruistic provider.” Until the data were analyzed, there would be no way for the enumerator in the field to detect if any particular respondent had a higher or lower preference for the health of their patients.

For each choice set, we assume that a provider will state a preference for a specified alternative if the expected utility from that alternative exceeds their expected utility from the other alternatives presented in the same choice set. For provider $i = 1, 2, \dots, N$, the probability of selecting alternative $j = 1, 2, \dots, J$ in choice set $s = 1, 2, \dots, S$ is shown below.

$$[3a] \quad P_{i,s,j} = \text{Prob}(y_{i,s} = j) = \text{Prob}(U_{i,s,j} \geq U_{i,s,k}) \forall j \neq k$$

We adopt a random utility model, where utility is composed of a systematic component and a random component:

$$[3b] \quad U_{i,s,j} = V_{i,s,j} + \mathcal{E}_{i,s,j}$$

Combining equations 3a and 3b, we have:

$$[3c] \quad P_{i,s,j} = \text{Prob}(\mathcal{E}_{i,s,j} - \mathcal{E}_{i,s,k} \geq V_{i,s,k} - V_{i,s,j}) \forall j \neq k$$

We further assume that the utility derived from a particular alternative is a function of that alternative’s attributes.

Since we are interested in assessing preferences of individual providers instead of an average effect, we adopt a mixed logit approach, allowing the coefficients on each attribute to be individual-specific. This preference heterogeneity induces correlation both over alternatives and over choice sets.

$$[4a] \quad U_{i,s,j} = \beta_{0i} + \beta_{1i} \text{Profit}_{i,s,j} + \beta_{2i} \text{Efficacy}_{i,s,j} + \beta_{3i} \text{FinancialBurden}_{i,s,j} + \mathcal{E}_{i,s,j}, \text{ where}$$

$$[4b] \quad \beta_{1i} = \bar{\beta}_1 + b_{1i}$$

$$[4c] \quad \beta_{2i} = \bar{\beta}_2 + b_{2i}$$

$$[4d] \quad \beta_{3i} = \bar{\beta}_3 + b_{3i}$$

These coefficients ($\beta_{1i}, \beta_{2i}, \beta_{3i}$) can be interpreted as the provider-specific marginal utility of profit, efficacy, and patient financial burden, respectively. β_{0i} is an individual-specific effect that would be constant across alternatives, and would thus drop out in estimation.

Under the mixed logit model, the conditional probability of provider i selecting alternative j in choice set s is given below. The coefficients $\beta_{1i}, \beta_{2i}, \beta_{3i}$ and corresponding attributes have been collapsed into the vectors β_i and $X_{i,s,j}$ for ease of notation.

$$[5] \quad (P_{i,s,j} | \beta_i) = \frac{\exp(\beta_i' X_{i,s,j})}{\sum_{j=1}^J \exp(\beta_i' X_{i,s,j})}$$

Similarly, the conditional probability of a set of choices over all choice tasks is as follows, where $y_{i,s,j}$ is a binary indicator for alternative j being selected by provider i in choice set s :

$$[6] \quad (P_{i,s,j} | \beta_i) = \prod_{s=1}^S \prod_{j=1}^J \left\{ \frac{\exp(\beta_i' X_{i,s,j})}{\sum_{j=1}^J \exp(\beta_i' X_{i,s,j})} \right\}^{y_{i,s,j}}$$

Integrating over the density $f(\beta | \theta)$, we obtain the unconditional probability of this set of choices. In our primary specification, we allow the three coefficients on profit, efficacy, and patient financial burden to be normally distributed, and allow for correlation between these random parameters. To simplify the process of assessing marginal substitution, we code profit as a continuous variable and efficacy and patient financial burden as categorical. However, we did test alternative specifications, including coding profit as categorical, allowing β_{1i} to be log-normally distributed. The models were compared using log-likelihood, AIC, and BIC to assess model fit.

$$[7] \quad P_i(\theta) = \int (P_i | \beta) f(\beta | \theta) d\beta$$

Our primary coefficients of interest are β_{1i} and β_{2i} for each provider, which reflect the response of the i -th provider to profit level and efficacy, respectively. A provider with a high mean β_{1i} can be regarded as having a higher marginal utility of profit than another provider with a low mean β_{1i} ; they care more about profit when deciding to sell a drug. Similarly, a provider with a higher mean β_{2i} has a higher marginal utility of product efficacy, etc. These respondent-specific propensities to prefer various attributes will be interpreted as being correlated with the marginal utility of that attribute. The marginal rate of substitution (MRS) was approximated as the ratio of β_{2i} , an indicator of marginal utility of efficacy, to β_{1i} , an indicator of the marginal utility of profit, and was standardized as a Z-score. A higher MRS reflects a greater relative value for treatment efficacy over profit; providers with a higher MRS are willing to sacrifice more profits for treatment efficacy as compared to providers with lower MRS. Because levels of profit and levels of efficacy in the survey were discrete values, our MRS indicator is limited by not being truly marginal, but rather incremental. The model was estimated with STATA 15.0 using the command `mixlogit`.

Based on the theory from the prior section we hypothesized that measures of technical quality would be positively correlated with the MRS between efficacy and profit.

IIIB. Technical Quality Measurement

As part of the social franchising intervention, these same 187 health providers were each evaluated within 12 months of the conjoint survey using observed pediatric patient simulations. The quality measurement algorithm has been previously validated and is described extensively elsewhere (Aung, 2012). It involved direct observation of provider performance using a trained evaluator. The provider was asked to assume that the evaluator was a mother who had brought in her sick child, represented by a life-sized medical mannequin. The evaluator then described a simulated case of a child with fever and waited for the provider to ask about the presenting symptoms. Her standardized responses were designed to lead to a presumed diagnosis of malaria. The provider was asked to conduct the diagnosis and treatment as normal. They were asked to verbalize pertinent questions and to verbally describe features of the child they would examine. Each provider received a score for diagnostic quality as well as a separate score for treatment quality. Symptoms of malaria are often non-specific, and a careless exam could lead to inaccurate diagnosis or inappropriate treatment (Mangham-Jefferies et al., 2014). This suggests that a malaria-based assessment would be a useful indicator of quality. As described by Aung et al. (2012) the scoring system was derived from WHO guidelines on malaria diagnosis and management in primary care and was validated by infectious disease specialists from Myanmar.

Plots and histograms of the quality variables were examined for normality. As can be seen in Figure 3, the provider scores for treatment and diagnostic quality appeared multimodal. Ordinary least squares models that ignore this bimodality would be a mis-specification of the data and lead to erroneous inferences. In order to appropriately fit the data, finite mixture models were used to assess the relationship between quality scores and predictors of quality, including provider MRS and \mathbf{X} , a vector of covariates for each provider, including age, sex, educational attainment, and occupation. The error term in a finite mixture regression model was assumed to follow a weighted distribution composed of the two separate normal distributions, as shown in Equation 6,

[6] $f(Quality) = (1 - p)N(\mu_1, \sigma_1) + pN(\mu_2, \sigma_2)$, where $(1 - p)$ and p are the probabilities of falling into class 1 and class 2, respectively and $N(\mu_k, \sigma_k)$ is the conditional probability density function for each response in the k -th class. The mixture models were fit and tested using the “fmm” command in Stata 15.

IV. RESULTS

Summary statistics of provider background characteristics and quality evaluation scores are shown in Table 1. Subjects were, on average, 31.06 years old, and one-third were female. Nearly two-thirds had completed primary

schooling, and 51% of providers considered their health care job to be their primary employment. Treatment quality scores fell between 0 and 37 (mean: 14.93, SD: 9.49), and diagnosis quality scores ranged from 0 to 55 (mean: 30.42, SD: 13.15).

Table 2 shows the mixed logit results analysis of the provider preference data. Model 1, our primary specification coding profit as a continuous and allowing all coefficients to be normally distributed, suggests that providers were more likely to prefer alternatives with higher efficacy and higher OOP expenditure. This confirms our finding during data collection that providers were interpreting OOP expenditure not as a patient burden but rather as assurance that they would be paid. The coefficient on profit was not statistically significant, and the large standard deviations suggest substantial variation in provider preferences. Model 2 shows similar results when coding profit categorically; we do not see a consistent increasing relationship between profit and likelihood of preference.

The provider-specific standardized MRS estimates from the mixed logit model are plotted in Figure 4, and display variation in the extent to which providers are willing to trade off a 1-unit increase in profit for higher drug efficacy (95% instead of 85%). The untransformed estimates show that $MU_{\pi} \geq 0$ for 87/187 providers and $MU_H \geq 0$ for 185/187 providers. The provider-specific standardized MRS estimates of OOP expenditure versus profit are plotted in Appendix Figure A1.

The distribution of provider quality scores is shown in Figure 3. Figure 3a plots total quality scores, which represent the sum of each provider's diagnosis score and treatment score. A kernel overlay suggests the presence of a bimodal distribution. Figure 3b and Figure 3c plot diagnosis quality scores and treatment quality scores, respectively. There is substantial variation in both scores across providers and the distribution of each appears multi-modal.

Table 3 and 4 show results from our primary analysis of the effect of provider preferences towards drug efficacy versus profit on quality of care, for diagnosis scores and treatment scores, respectively. Because these are mixture models, each regression generates two sets of coefficients. Class 1 provides coefficients governing the conditional mean of the leftward component of the mixture, and class 2 provides coefficients governing the rightward component of the mixture. The probabilities at the bottom of the table (Pr1, Pr2) represent the proportion of the mixture distribution accounted for by class 1 (leftward) and class 2 (rightward), respectively. The marginal mean of quality scores for each class are also shown.

All models included covariates for provider age and sex, and indicators for whether or not the provider had completed primary schooling, and whether or not healthcare was considered their primary job. We also control for provider township. Robust standard errors accounting for clustering at the township level are shown for each coefficient.

The finite mixture models show no relationship between preferences towards drug efficacy and diagnosis quality scores (Table 3) in both classes and a statistically significant negative effect of preferences towards profit on scores in Model 2 and Model 3 in class 1. In model 4, we find no statistically significant relationship between MRS and provider diagnosis scores in either class.

In the models of treatment quality scores (Table 4), mixture Model 1 finds a statistically significant positive effect of provider preferences towards efficacy on treatment quality scores in both classes, with a higher magnitude effect in class 2 (rightward component). Model 2 finds no statistically significant relationship between provider preferences toward profit and treatment quality in class 1, but a significant negative effect in class 2. Mixture Model 3, which controls for both preferences towards efficacy and preferences towards profit, finds a significant positive effect of provider preferences towards efficacy on treatment quality in both classes, with the effect higher in magnitude among class 2 (rightward component). Finally, Mixture Model 4 finds a significant negative effect of provider MRS on treatment quality scores in class 1 (leftward component).

Appendix tables A2 and A3 repeat this analysis for diagnosis and treatment quality scores coding profit as a categorical variable. As in our primary analysis, we find a significant positive effect of the marginal utility of efficacy on treatment scores, which persists in class 1 even after controlling for the marginal utility of profit. These models also find a significant positive effect of provider MRS on treatment quality in class 1.

V. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

Our study suggests that providers who reveal a stronger preference towards drug efficacy (patient health benefit) scored higher on assessments of quality of treatment of children with malaria, controlling for patient preferences towards profit. We find some evidence that providers who have greater preferences towards drug profit have lower quality of diagnosis, although this is not consistent across all models. It seems plausible that provider preferences may be more directly associated with treatment choices, as this is the primary driver of revenue in the Myanmar context. We did not find a consistent association between provider MRS of efficacy relative to profit and

quality of care, although there is some evidence that among the lower-performing providers, MRS is *negatively* associated with quality of treatment.

The theoretical hypotheses were that providers are not purely profit-maximizing, and that the MRS of drug efficacy versus profit would be positively associated with the quality of care; we predicted that providers who would be willing to sacrifice profits to achieve greater patient health benefit would also be providing higher quality care. The evidence supports the idea that all providers are not purely profit maximizing, as our conjoint analysis demonstrates that higher drug efficacy is associated with likelihood of preferring a drug, after controlling for drug profit. Although we find substantial variation in these provider preferences, and evidence that these preferences do affect quality of care, our results stop short of a clear effect of MRS. We believe our measure of preferences towards profit were imprecise and may have been complicated by the misinterpretation of OOP being a measure of certainty of payment. This is a limitation of our study.

The relationship between provider altruism and quality of care has not been thoroughly explored empirically. However, the relationship between hospital-level altruism, which may be characterized by not-for-profit status, and quality of care has been investigated. Some evidence exists that not-for-profit hospitals, which are presumably motivated by factors other than profits and re-invest revenues into their services, may provide higher quality care than for-profit hospitals. A systematic review concluded that mortality is lower in not-for-profit hospitals than in for-profit hospitals (Herrera, 2014), although the empirical evidence related to overall quality of care is mixed (Rotarius, 2006; Keeler, 1992; Devereaux, 2002; Landon, 2008).

One limitation of this study is that it only sampled 187 rural providers in Myanmar. None of the providers were physicians, and only about half consider providing healthcare to be their primary job. The relationships between provider preferences and quality of care may be different within different contexts or among providers with more formal clinical training. Furthermore, the measurement of provider preferences and quality can be imprecise. Preferences derived from the conjoint survey may suffer from measurement error due to respondent fatigue, confusion or misunderstanding related to the choice questions, respondent inattention, or the use of decision heuristics that are inconsistent with our model of decision-making (Johnson et al, 2013). Unfortunately, our measurement of preferences towards patient financial burden as well as profit was flawed. In our study, we measured quality of care through a simulation focused on malaria. Had we used a different approach or a different patient vignette, our distribution of quality scores might have been different.

Stated preference studies are also susceptible to reporting errors. Obfuscation to achieve social acceptability is quite common in surveys with direct questions regarding socially acceptable behaviors. However, social acceptability would be hard for respondents to demonstrate on a conjoint survey since it would be quite challenging for a respondent to assess any particular medication profile as the socially acceptable one to endorse. One advantage of conjoint and discrete choice methods to measure preferences is that they are indirect (Pederson et al., 2012). Providers are not directly confronted with a socially-laden question of how much they prefer money relative to patient health outcomes. Providers simply make a series of choices between drugs that they might like to sell based on attributes of the drugs. The quality measurement is unusually strong in this study because it is based on direct observation of diagnosis and treatment using a simulated patient under an algorithm that was previously validated in Myanmar (Aung, 2012).

Prior literature has acknowledged that health provider preferences extend beyond financial remuneration. However, because measurement of provider preferences is challenging, it is rare to observe the extent of heterogeneity in these preferences. Our paper contributes to existing literature in two primary ways. The first is that our data emphasize that there is substantial variation in the intensity of preferences for patient outcomes relative to provider profit. Not all providers are altruistic, and not all are pure profit maximizers. The second main contribution is to demonstrate that provider preferences matter because they are correlated with technical quality of clinical prescribing.

VI. Policy Implications

This study shows that informal health care providers in rural Myanmar have heterogeneous preferences in their willingness to trade off higher profits for greater treatment efficacy. We found that among providers with a stronger preference for treatment efficacy, the treatment provided is of greater quality than that of those providers who place less weight on efficacy.

Our data would not be consistent with models of provider behavior that assume the sole motivation is financial gain. More specifically, our results demonstrate that there is heterogeneity across providers in the extent of altruistic motivation, and that preferences towards patient health benefit do affect provider behavior. Quality-based payment systems have become widespread and are encouraged by the Institute of Medicine (Corrigan, 2001). Evidence of heterogeneous provider motivations suggests that performance-based payment systems may not be efficient for all providers. Specifically, those providers whose intrinsic motivation to promote patient health propels

them towards quality may not require the same payments as providers with less intrinsic motivation. In theory, payments tied to performance among providers who naturally have a stronger preference for patient health outcomes could be reduced. Previous work by Siciliani (2009) supports the idea that financial incentives alone may not be optimal, suggesting that providers with intermediate levels of altruism may not respond to higher payment. Screening mechanisms to selectively recruit those providers with strong preferences toward patient outcomes and to provide them with emotional and cognitive rewards, rather than monetary rewards, may be a promising policy.

Appealing to health provider altruism is beginning to play a larger part in strategies to improve quality of care. Professional codes of ethics have long been used to socialize providers in a culture of selfless sacrifice during medical training, and recent literature has served as a call for a renewed sense of this professional duty (Mueller, 2015; Misch, 2002; DeAngelis, 2015; Crandall, 2009). Other recent initiatives have focused primarily on leveraging provider preferences towards patient health outcomes. The 16-site nationwide “Aligning Forces for Quality” program launched by the Robert Wood Johnson Foundation, for example, focused on providing transparent and public reporting of provider performance (Christianson, 2016). Similarly, the “MyPOD” program instituted at a children’s hospital in Wilmington, DE, relied on electronic medical record data as well as self-reporting by surgeons, to track and target surgeon-specific outcomes (Berman, 2017). Additional programs have focused on assessing patient satisfaction to improve quality of care (Barr, 2006; Harris, 1999; Arnetz, 1996). However, while these outcomes and satisfaction data are intended to improve quality, any effect may be driven by provider concern for their reputation or professional status rather than a purely altruistic motivation.

Ultimately, our data from rural Myanmar are not consistent with the hypothesis that all health care providers care solely about their profits. The preferences towards patient health benefit that we observed among informal providers were heterogeneous. Furthermore, this study suggested that these preferences mattered for the quality of patient care. We found that, in general, the more providers care about patient health outcomes, the higher quality treatment they provide. Our results showed that most of the providers we studied were concerned with the health of their patients, although these preferences varied substantially.

VI. REFERENCES

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